

THE CRASHWORTHINESS DESIGN OF TRANSPORT AIRCRAFT USING COMPOSITE STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

The crashworthiness of composite structure attracts more and more attentions for the rapid growth utilization in transport aircraft. To better understand its crashworthy structure design approach, the crashworthiness design methods are reviewed and discussed. The crashworthy design concept is introduced first, and different components play different roles during impact process. Then, the fuselage frame, strut and bottom structure are investigated. Not only the conventional transport aircraft but also some innovative structures of experimental test and numerical simulation are discussed. The prospect of crashworthy transport aircraft is given from three aspects including numerical simulation, impact dynamic performance and design method.

1 INTRODUCTION

The crashworthiness is one of the most important structural performances for transport aircraft because it is involving the safety of occupant during impact accident. To guarantee the survival probability of passage, there are many provisions associated with crashworthiness in the airworthiness regulations [1]. To guarantee the safety of occupant, aircraft structure should be proper designed to dissipate the impact kinetic energy. A number of researches are conducted on the crashworthiness of transport aircraft [2-3]. However, a majority of the studies are the metal transport aircraft.

Composite material has been extensively used in the design of aircraft structure due to their high structural performance. However, the crashworthiness design of aircraft composite structure is one of the most challenging problems in aerospace engineering. The failure behaviour of composite structure is great different with that of metal aircraft. The brittle failure mode is the usual way for carbon/epoxy composite instead of plastic deformation. Consequently, the design concept of transport aircraft is the hot research topic, and the equivalent energy absorption ability of composite structure with that of metal transport aircraft is one of the most important and challenging problems.

To better understand the transport aircraft crashworthiness design concept using composite material, the design concept of composite material in aircraft structure is reviewed and discussed. Based on the available experimental test and numerical simulation result, the transport aircraft crashworthiness design method based on composite material is prospected. The corresponding content of this paper would guide the composite transport aircraft structure design in the future.

2 CRASHWORTHINESS DESIGN CONCEPT

For the crashworthy transport aircraft, it should have two important abilities including the survivable living volume for passage and the limited impact load transmitted to passages. The generic

design concept of transport aircraft is given in Ref. [4]. The energy absorption structure of transport aircraft is the design key aspect for crashworthy concept, and the typical design method is exhibited as Figure 1. Three components including frame, strut and bottom structure are the most important energy absorption devices for transport aircraft. The frame could absorb nearly half of impact kinetic energy by plastic hinges for metal transport, and it determines the failure mode of entire transport [5]. The strut could not only dissipate some part of impact energy, but also alter the failure behavior of frame. The same with the above two components, the bottom structure has the greatest influence on the initial impact load, and it also plays important roles in energy absorbing. Most of the researches are focused on the improvement of energy absorption ability for frame, strut and bottom structure. However, the crashworthiness design concept of composite transport aircraft is still a challenging problem.

Figure 1: The energy absorption structure in transport aircraft

3 COMPONENTS DESIGN OF TRANSPORT AIRCRAFT

Transport aircraft consists of many components, and frame, bottom structure and strut are the three important aspects of aircraft crashworthiness design. Three above aspects have been investigated by institutes and university in the USA, European and China, etc. Research of the entire transport aircraft is still a very difficult problem for crashworthiness, most of previous studies is about the typical composite structures.

3.1 Frame

The fuselage frame is the most important energy absorption component of transport aircraft, and it could dissipate nearly half of the impact kinetic energy. Although the above conclusion is obtained from metal transport aircraft, the frame also has the greatest role in crashworthiness design. To better understand the failure behaviour of frame, many researches are conducted. The effect of floor placement on the impact dynamics performance of fuselage is investigated by Lisa using experimental and analytical methods. The frames of circular fuselage consist of graphite-epoxy composite material, and floor is simulated with steel beam. The skin is combined with frame because torsional instability of frame appears for the absence of skin [6]. The fuselage frame for crashworthiness is optimized by Woodson, and Vlasov type beam theory is adopted [7]. The circular circumferential frame segments under impact load are experimental tested and numerical simulated with LS-DYNA shown as Figure 2. The load-displacement history curve is reasonable correlation between the simulation and tests [8]. The generic composite frame with carbon fibre/epoxy Heimbs is tested, and the numerical model is developed in ABAQUS. The frame breaking, skin damage under bending and joint failure are the key aspects for energy absorption [9].

The high specific strength and stiffness is the great advantage of composite, but the brittle failure mechanism instead of plastic deformation of CFRP frame is one of the most challenging for crashworthiness design shown in Figure 3 [10-11]. The equivalent crashworthiness of composite frame with metal frame is the design objective. The frame is suffered bending load during crash for the cylindrical shape. A novel crash concept of twin-walled fuselage panels with fold core having

progressive frame failure is proposed by Sturm [10]. The sandwich structures with four configurations of embedded ply-drop triggering mechanisms are experimental analyzed and compared [12]. The kinematics model is given for the aircraft fuselage which could be used in the aircraft preliminary design stage. The crash devices are defined with macro elements, and other structures are modeled by linear elastically shown as Figure 4 [13].

Although many researches of the composite frame are conducted, its crashworthiness performance is still not well understood. Nearly all of experimental test and numerical simulation are carried out in the simplified impact condition, but the realistic impact condition is very complicated. The impact dynamic performance under complex environment needs further investigation. In addition, the design concept to improve the energy absorption ability and failure behavior of frame must be studied.

Figure 2: Frame experimental test

Figure 3: Frame failure of metallic and CFRP composite material.

Figure 4: Kinematics model approach for aircraft fuselage

3.2 Strut

Strut is the supporting structure under the cabin floor, which is not only employed as the energy absorption structure without redesign the original fuselage structure but also alter the failure modes of fuselage. The channel section is the regular structural type for strut, and some researches are conducted for this kind of structure. The result shows that the corner element is the most efficient for energy absorption per unit mass by Feraboli [14].

A composite energy absorption tube with tearing failure behaviour for the strut of commercial aircraft is proposed by Heimbs shown as Figure 5. The carbon/epoxy prepreg laminate with 50% fibres in 0° (axial) and 45° direction is employed as the material types, and it would be cut into stripes. The composite tube would be suffered axial compression during the impact process because of the absorber device. There are just two peaks of impact load including trigger load and deflection device, and stable impact load and failure behavior are exhibited [15]. This kind of strut provides a better choose for the crashworthy design of transport aircraft.

Figure 5: Composite strut with tearing failure model.

Sine-wave beam is adopted as the energy absorption devices between the under-floor beam and frame given by Wiggeraad shown as Figure 6. The sine-wave beam has a small angle considering the rotation of frame. Although no trigger detail is exhibited, the ply drop-off trigger is employed to reduce the initial impact load. An expected failure model with outward direction failure instead of stable compression is demonstrated [16]. The experiment provides insight about the failure behavior of under floor structure although it is unsuccessful. The effect of oblique struts on the crashworthiness of fuselage section is investigated by Feng. Al-7075 is the material type of oblique strut, and the fuselage skin is made of T300/QY8911 in the research [17].

Figure 6: Sine-wave beam composite strut with tearing failure model.

The crashworthiness design of strut is very difficult for the supporting condition between cabin floor and frame, and its impact dynamics becomes very complicated for the vibration and rotation of structural support. Besides, the lightening holes in the strut exist in the practical structure. Consequently, not only the low initial impact load and stable failure behavior are the important characteristics of crashworthy strut, but also the sensitivity with respect to boundary condition and manufacturing technique must be considered.

3.3 Bottom structure

The bottom structure collides with impact ground or water first which not only determines the initial peak impact load and but also affects the energy absorption ability of transport aircraft. There are two typical design concepts for bottom structure. The first design method is based on the original transport aircraft structure. The half tube CFRP components under the cargo crossbeam of transport aircraft is experimental investigated for axial crushing condition is studied by Waimer shown in Figure 7. Although just simple half tube is conducted, the experimental test is proper developed similar with the realistic impact condition [18]. The tension mechanisms of the cabin and cargo floor in the crash devices is employed to absorb impact kinetic energy by Schatrow, and it has several advantage such as reduced structural mass penalty shown in Figure 8 [19]. The second design concept has redesigned the

frame to arrange the bottom energy absorption, and frame is regarded as the supporting structure for bottom structure. Sine-wave beam is located in the under-floor frame by Delsart shown as Figure 9, and carbon fabrics and aramid fabrics composite are adopted. The impact ground and under-floor beam provide the crushing platform, and the stable failure behavior is expected. However, the frame above the sine-wave beam ruptures during the impact accident. This design concept utilizes an innovative frame, and the bottom frame is redesigned to arrange the energy absorption structure. This design concept is good attempt for aircraft crashworthiness design [20].

Although the impact test is conducted for energy absorption components of bottom structure, it may totally failure instead of progressive failure during impact process for the boundary condition. In addition, the structure having frame, cargo crossbeam and framework, etc on the bottom of transport aircraft is much complicated. To obtain the best crashworthy transport aircraft structure, the experimental test and numerical simulation must be conducted in realistic complex boundary condition.

Figure 7: The energy absorber under the cargo crossbeam.

Figure 8: The energy absorber under the cargo crossbeam.

Figure 9: Sine-wave beam composite under the frame.

4 FUTURE OUTLOOKS

The crashworthiness of composite transport aircraft is still a very difficult problem compared with metal type. Firstly, the effective and reliable numerical simulation method is under development. Most of the available composite approaches are phenomena-based failure models. In these methods, many parameters are dependent on the experimental result, and some of them could not be directly given by experimental test. Consequently, experimental test is most efficient approach for crashworthiness

research, but available experimental results are rarely for the expensive cost. Secondly, the failure behaviour having brittle failure, bending, fragmentation, splaying and local buckling is very complicated, and it would be affected by the uncertainty factors such as boundary condition, manufacturing technique and impact load. There is great difference between realistic impact boundary condition of transport aircraft and simple experimental and numerical test. The robust composite structure must be further researched. Finally, most of the previous studies are just single test of component, but the frame, strut and bottom structure have strong coupling effect. All of the components must be considered during crashworthiness design to give better transport aircraft. To achieve best structure, the coupling effect between different components and their design optimization method should be investigated.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The paper reviews and discusses the crashworthiness design approach for composite transport aircraft. The impact dynamic performance of composite structure is great different from that of metal structure. The design concept of composite transport aircraft is similar with that of metal type, but its brittle failure mechanism instead of plastic deformation is the great challenging. Although there are a number of improvement methods for composite transport aircraft, it is still a very challenging problem for numerical simulation method, robust composite structure and coupling effecting between components.

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